

Proto-respiration is the physical basis of life

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Cellular energy is stored in H₂O and CH₂O. The cathode in proto-respiration can be both O₂ and CO₂. The O₂ pathway is the standard proto-respiration pathway, and the latter is for production of carbohydrates, (CH₂O)_n. When the anode in proto-respiration, water (more specifically, hydroxide ions, alkaline water), is "boosted" with carbohydrates, the cathode is the oxygen that was substituted by CO₂ in the carbohydrate pathway of proto-respiration.

The reduction at the cathode in either proto-respiration pathway (oxygen or carbon dioxide) is with hydrogen gas, formed from reduction of hydrogen ions in acid compartment of the acid-base electrochemical cell. $O_2 + 2 H_2 \rightarrow 2 H_2O$ and $CO_2 + 2 H_2 \rightarrow H_2O + CH_2O$. In both the water and glucose pathways, the oxidation at the anode is in hydroxide ions, the alkaline compartment in the acid-base electrochemical cell. $4 \cdot OH \rightarrow 2H_2O + O_2$ and $CH_2O + 4 \cdot OH \rightarrow 3 H_2O + CO_2$, electrons released when hydroxide ions oxidized to hydroxyl radicals.

To articulate it as simply as possible, cellular energy is stored in H₂O and CH₂O. The cathode in proto-respiration can be both O₂ and CO₂. The three pathways, acid-base cell, carbohydrate production, and carbohydrate discharge, have the same chemical reactions. In all three, the cathode is reduced with hydrogen gas, from hydrogen ions and electrons, and the anode is oxidized with hydroxyl radicals from hydroxide ions. The anode is the same in the acid-base and carbohydrate producing pathways, and the cathode is the same in the acid-base and carbohydrate discharge pathway. Three pathways, two anodes, two cathodes.

Protoplasm favours the decomposition of water, proto-respiration, because it has physically removed hydrogen from it. It is alkaline. The removal of H from H₂O shifts the redox balance between water and oxygen towards O₂.

The protoplasm is kept in a chemically inert state at rest. Proto-respiration takes place when the adsorbed alkali, potassium and polarized water, hydrated hydroxide, desorbs and liquifies.

The alkaline cell forms from potassium hydroxide. Cells are inherently able to accumulate potassium, this was documented by Sidney Fox in 1981. Fox made what he called "microspheres", he simply boiled protein in water and it coalesced into little "cells". These "cells" would accumulate K⁺ from surrounding medium up to 1600x that in the medium.

The reason for the potassium accumulation is likely explained by the polarization of water in electromagnetic fields. Water aligns along the field lines, and prefers to form a unique phase that Gerald Pollack calls the "gel phase". This structure is an electrical double layer, one layer is hydrated hydroxide, and it excludes hydrogen ions that form the other layer next to it. This "ice-like" double layer causes the phenomena of surface tension on water.

Potassium has higher attractive force to the hydrated hydroxide gel as a "magnet" (and sodium to a lesser extent) and likely just substitutes the H⁺. Cells therefore spontaneously become alkaline, and can operate on electrical current from the redox balance between water and oxygen. Anode: $4 \text{ OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{ e}^-$, cathode: $4 \text{ e}^- + 4 \text{ H}^+ + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$.

Why potassium (and sodium as well) has higher attractive force than the hydrogen ions, they have more protons. That attractive force, electronegativity, increases with number of protons from left to right in periodic table is well known. It at the same time tends to decrease down the rows because distance to nucleus increases, but that is only the case when distance is limiting factor. Long range attraction still increases.

The adsorption of a cation with stronger attractive force to the gel explains why addition of salts like sodium chloride or potassium chloride to water increases surface tension.

What about Liebig's hypothesis that organic acids were intermediaries in carbohydrate production since there are organic acids in fruits? These acids are likely analogous to the role of water in adsorption of potassium against the structured gel water. Remember, water can be turned into a potassium-adsorption mechanism because it is technically an acid, it can release a hydrogen ion and gain a net negative charge. It can then turn this net negative charge into a huge mass of hydroxide ions, hydrated hydroxide gel. The hydrogen cations are forced to the outside of this gel, they can no longer get close to their conjugate anion, and no longer have an advantage against alkali metals further down the periodic table.

Anion polymers might in general tend to demote hydrogen ions as their conjugate cation. Since potassium is preferentially adsorbed onto gel water over hydrogen ions because the gel means distance is not the limiting factor, the tartrate (and other anions of the organic acids) likely form ordered structures as well. Fruits are likely acidic during maturation because tartrate and malate gels are how fruits accumulate potassium that will nourish the embryo in the seed.

The insulating layer of sodium and chloride that surround cells, is visible in electron photographs as a thin dark layer of sodium cations and a thicker lighter layer of chloride anions outside of it. This appearance is an optical artefact from the electron microscope, positive charge acts as a convergent lens, making the cation layer appear denser, and, narrower, and negative charge is a divergent lens with opposite effect. This insulation contributes to separating the hydrogen ion cathode from the hydroxide ion gel anode of the cell.